

A Study on the Integration of Production Planning and Control (PPC) with ERP Systems: Benefits and Challenges for the Industry

*Um estudo sobre a Integração do Planejamento e Controle da
Produção (PCP) com Sistemas ERP: Benefícios e Desafios para a
Indústria*

*Un Estudio sobre la Integración de la Planificación y Control de la
Producción (PCP) con los Sistemas ERP: Beneficios y Desafíos para
la Industria*

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Abstract: Insert the abstract here, in Calibri font size 10 italics. Respect the indentation from the second line of the summary. The abstract should be between 100 and 200 words. In recent decades, the industry has faced increasing challenges resulting from globalization, technological advances, and changes in consumer behavior, requiring greater production efficiency and process integration. In this context, Production Planning and Control (PPC) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems emerge as strategic tools to optimize operations, reduce costs, and improve decision-making. The objective of this study was to analyze the benefits and challenges arising from the integration between PPC and ERP in the industrial sector. To this end, a bibliographic and descriptive approach was adopted, including a literature review based on relevant books and scientific articles. The results show that integration provides greater operational efficiency, real-time visibility, inventory reduction, and strategic alignment among departments, while also facing barriers such as high costs, cultural resistance, and technical complexity. It is concluded that although PPC–ERP integration is strategic for industrial competitiveness, its success depends on proper planning, staff training, and continuous system monitoring.

Keywords: *Competitiveness; Integration; Technology.*

Resumo: Nas últimas décadas, a indústria tem enfrentado desafios crescentes decorrentes da globalização, avanços tecnológicos e mudanças no perfil de consumo, exigindo maior eficiência produtiva e integração de processos. Nesse contexto, o Planejamento e Controle da Produção (PCP) e os sistemas *Enterprise Resource Planning* (ERP), ou Planejamento de Recursos Empresariais, emergem como ferramentas estratégicas para otimizar operações, reduzir custos e melhorar a tomada de decisão. O objetivo deste estudo foi analisar os benefícios e desafios decorrentes da integração PCP–ERP na indústria. Para tanto, adotou-se uma abordagem bibliográfica e descritiva, com revisão de literatura, incluindo livros e artigos científicos relevantes. Os resultados evidenciam que a integração proporciona maior eficiência operacional, visibilidade em tempo real, redução de estoques e alinhamento estratégico entre áreas, ao

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mesmo tempo em que enfrenta barreiras como custos elevados, resistência cultural e complexidade técnica. Conclui-se que, embora a integração PCP–ERP seja estratégica para a competitividade industrial, seu sucesso depende de planejamento, capacitação de equipes e monitoramento contínuo dos sistemas.

Palavras-chave: Competitividade; Integração; Tecnologia.

Resumen: En las últimas décadas, la industria ha enfrentado desafíos crecientes derivados de la globalización, los avances tecnológicos y los cambios en el perfil de consumo, lo que exige una mayor eficiencia productiva e integración de procesos. En este contexto, la Planificación y Control de la Producción (PCP) y los sistemas de Planificación de Recursos Empresariales (ERP) surgen como herramientas estratégicas para optimizar las operaciones, reducir costos y mejorar la toma de decisiones. El objetivo de este estudio fue analizar los beneficios y desafíos resultantes de la integración entre PCP y ERP en la industria. Para ello, se adoptó un enfoque bibliográfico y descriptivo, con revisión de la literatura, incluyendo libros y artículos científicos relevantes. Los resultados evidencian que la integración proporciona mayor eficiencia operativa, visibilidad en tiempo real, reducción de inventarios y alineación estratégica entre las áreas, al mismo tiempo que enfrenta barreras como altos costos, resistencia cultural y complejidad técnica. Se concluye que, aunque la integración PCP–ERP es estratégica para la competitividad industrial, su éxito depende de la planificación, la capacitación de los equipos y el monitoreo continuo de los sistemas.

Palabras clave: Competitividad; Integración; Tecnología.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, industries have faced an increasingly competitive landscape, driven by market globalization, technological advancements, and changes in consumer profiles. This context demands greater productive efficiency and integrated process management to ensure the sustainability and competitiveness of organizations (Slack; Brandon-Jones; Johnston, 2020). In this environment, Production Planning and Control (PPC) assumes a strategic role by aligning market demand with the company's productive capacity. In practical terms, PPC is responsible for planning, scheduling, and monitoring production execution, ensuring the efficient use of resources and strict adherence to established deadlines (Corrêa; Corrêa, 2017). However, when analyzed in isolation, PPC faces significant limitations, particularly due to its lack of integration with other organizational sectors.

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems emerge as robust platforms that centralize information and integrate various areas of the company, such as purchasing, finance, inventory, sales, and human resources. This integration allows for greater fluidity in internal communication and promotes data consistency, fundamental aspects of the decision-making process (Davenport, 1998; Laudon & Laudon, 2015).

The convergence between Production Planning and Control (PPC) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is therefore a significant advancement for modern industry, as it provides greater visibility into the value chain, optimization of productive resources, cost reduction, and more reliable delivery times. Furthermore, this integration fosters faster, more assertive decisions by effectively aligning the operational, tactical, and strategic levels (Tubino, 2017).

However, despite the benefits, the integration process is not without challenges. Barriers such as high implementation costs, resistance to organizational change, the need for qualified professionals, and technical risks associated with constant changes in ERP systems are widely reported in case studies and practical experience (Oliveira, 2018; Griend; Kusters; Trienekens, 2024). These difficulties highlight the need for a critical, comprehensive analysis of the real impacts of this integration in the industrial context.

The relevance of this study is justified by the growing demand from organizations for integrated solutions that increase the efficiency of production processes and strengthen strategic decision-making. Given that industrial competitiveness largely depends on the ability to align resources, deadlines, and quality, it is essential to understand how integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) with Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) can help overcome production bottlenecks and improve organizational performance. Moreover, by analyzing the benefits and challenges of this integration, this article seeks to provide theoretical and practical guidance to help managers and researchers adopt more effective practices in the contemporary industrial context.

Thus, the objective of this article is to analyze the benefits and challenges arising from integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) with ERP systems in industry. The research is developed through a literature review, contributing to a

broader understanding of the effects of this synergy on productive efficiency and organizational competitiveness.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Production planning and control (PPC) plays a central role in modern industrial management, aligning market demand with the company's production capacity. As stated by Tubino (2017), PPC seeks to ensure the rational use of available resources and to program and control the production flow to meet deadlines, costs, and quality requirements. In other words, its strategic function is to reduce uncertainties and avoid imbalances between supply and demand.

In this context, Corrêa and Corrêa (2017) emphasize that production planning and control (PPC) serves as a link between the organization's functional areas, enabling production to be conducted in an integrated manner. As the authors claim, the absence of a structured PPC can lead to scheduling failures, excessive inventory, and delivery disruptions, thereby compromising the company's competitiveness. In turn, ERP systems emerged to integrate organizational processes into a single database. Davenport (1998, p. 123) states:

ERP systems promise to integrate all the information that flows through a company – financial, human resources, supply chain, and customer information – into a single, unified system.

This characteristic transforms ERP into a strategic management tool capable of reducing redundancies, promoting standardization, and facilitating decision-making at all organizational levels (Laudon; Laudon, 2015).

As stated by Slack, Brandon-Jones, and Johnston (2020), integrating production planning and control (PPC) with ERP enables production planning to be fed with real-time information on inventory, sales, purchases, and finances. This increases decision reliability and generates greater synergy across areas, eliminating rework and waste. Oliveira (2018) adds that aligning these systems is fundamental for the company to anticipate demand, adjust production capacity, and reduce operational costs.

In this regard, both Production Planning and Control (PPC) and ERP systems play complementary roles in industrial management. While the former organizes and coordinates production operations, the latter centralizes and integrates business information. The convergence of these tools leads to significant gains in competitiveness, productivity, and organizational efficiency.

2.1 The Role of the PCP in Industry

Planning and control (PPC) are generally divided into three levels: strategic, tactical, and operational. At the strategic level, it establishes guidelines for production and capacity investments. At the tactical level, it contributes to the creation of integrated plans and the organization of the production sequence. At the operational level, the focus is on managing the shop floor and executing production orders (Corrêa; Corrêa 2017).

In accordance with Tubino (2017), the lack of an effective production planning and control (PPC) system can lead to high costs, problems in meeting demand, and underutilization of productive resources. Thus, to remain competitive in complex industrial environments, it is increasingly necessary to integrate it with robust information systems, such as ERP systems.

Furthermore, as Mäule and Götte (2025) point out, the adoption of data-driven production planning and control (PPC) approaches represents a fundamental trend in Industry 4.0. Despite its potential to increase efficiency, flexibility, and responsiveness, its implementation still faces significant challenges, including barriers to entry, technical constraints, and data quality issues.

2.2 ERP as an Integration Tool

ERP systems evolved from early Material Requirements Planning (MRP) software, expanding their scope beyond materials and production management. Currently, they encompass the entire enterprise, enabling the integration of financial, commercial, and logistical data into a single environment (Davenport, 1998).

According to Oliveira (2018), implementing an ERP reduces data inconsistencies and improves operational traceability. This directly affects Production Planning and Control (PPC), enabling it to operate with more accurate, timely data, hence facilitating production planning and scheduling. Besides, integrating ERP and PPC strengthens the supply chain by including suppliers and customers in the information flow, thereby promoting greater cooperation and transparency.

However, as highlighted by Griend, Kusters, and Trienekens (2024), robust ERP systems can pose significant operational risks, including code defects, the need for successive repairs, and unplanned impacts on production, these factors demonstrate that, despite the centralization and integration of information provided by ERP systems, their implementation requires ongoing attention and proper maintenance procedures to avoid disruptions to the production flow.

2.3 PCP-ERP Integration and Industry 4.0

The Fourth Industrial Revolution, also known as Industry 4.0, has intensified the need for integration between management systems. As maintained by Silva (2021), technologies such as Big Data and the Internet of Things (IoT) accelerate the flow of real-time data, making platforms such as ERP systems essential for consolidating information.

In this context, production planning and control (PPC) also benefit from implementing digital tools that grant more accurate demand forecasting, process optimization, and more efficient resource allocation. Slack, Brandon-Jones, and Johnston (2020) highlight that incorporating digital systems into PPC provides greater agility and adaptability to market fluctuations, making organizations more resilient.

Furthermore, as argued by Kasper et al. (2024), technological advances in

Industry 4.0 allow production planning and control (PPC) structures to evolve into centralized or decentralized models that combine human judgment and automated intelligence to optimize production planning and control. These modern structures concede real-time decision-making, more effective resource coordination and rapid adaptation to changes, reinforcing the importance of effective integration between PPC and ERP.

Mäule and Götte (2025) argue that, despite advances enabled by digitization and integration with ERP systems, significant gaps remain in understanding the practical challenges companies face, particularly in maintaining reliable data and managing the complexity of system integration. This reinforces the need for critical analysis that considers not only the benefits but also the limitations inherent in the digital transformation of production.

3. METHOD

For this study, a methodology based on bibliographic and descriptive research was adopted, considering that the main objective is to analyze the benefits and challenges of integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) and ERP systems in the industry. According to Gil (2019), bibliographic research aims to provide greater familiarity with the problem, clarifying it and contributing to the formulation of initial hypotheses and interpretations.

Thus, a comprehensive bibliographic review was conducted on the concepts of Production Planning and Control (PPC), ERP systems, and their intersection in the context of industrial management. To this end, classic works on Production Management were consulted, such as Tubino (2017), Corrêa and Corrêa (2017), and Slack, Brandon-Jones, and Johnston (2020), as well as scientific articles published in national and international journals, which allowed for a solid understanding of the subject.

Subsequently, a descriptive research approach was chosen, as defined by Turrioni and Mello (2012), which involves recording, analyzing, and correlating facts or phenomena without direct manipulation to observe their characteristics and relationships. In the present study, this approach enabled the description and correlation of documented cases of industrial companies that implemented integration between Production Planning and Control (PPC) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), identifying the practices, benefits, and obstacles encountered.

Secondary data collection was conducted through searches of consolidated academic databases, such as ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Scopus, covering the period from 2015 to 2024, a time when the debate on Industry 4.0 and the digitalization of industrial processes gained prominence. The inclusion criteria adopted were:

- Articles that specifically addressed PCP-ERP integration;
- Research that presented applicable results or critical assessments of advantages and challenges;
- Articles published in national or international journals, ensuring diversity

and relevance of sources.

Finally, the collected data were organized into comparative tables that summarized the main benefits and challenges identified. This organization enabled a critical, integrated analysis that considered different perspectives and industrial contexts, hence strengthening understanding of the practical impacts of PCP-ERP integration on productive efficiency and organizational competitiveness.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After reviewing the literature and analyzing relevant studies, the main contributions and limitations of integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) with ERP systems in industry were identified. The results show that although the benefits are significant, substantial challenges require strategic planning, team training, and continuous system maintenance.

4.1 BENEFITS OF PCP-ERP INTEGRATION

According to Kasper et al. (2024), integrating production planning and control (PPC) structures with ERP systems grants the transformation of operational data into strategic decisions, consequently promoting greater efficiency, visibility, and responsiveness in industrial operations. Table 1 summarizes the main benefits reported in the literature across both operational and strategic perspectives.

The analysis of the presented benefits shows that the integration between Production Planning and Control (PPC) and ERP is not limited to a one-off operational improvement but represents a strategic advancement for modern industry. By combining real-time information, cross-functional coordination, and process automation, organizations can reduce rework, optimize inventory, anticipate demand, and make more assertive decisions, thereby promoting greater competitiveness and efficiency (Kasper et al., 2024; Griend; Kusters; Trienekens, 2024).

While the benefits are significant, implementing this integration faces barriers that, if not properly managed, can compromise results. Therefore, it is essential to examine the main challenges companies face when jointly adopting Production Planning and Control (PPC) and ERP systems, to qualify a balanced understanding of the potential gains and operational obstacles.

Table 1 – Benefits of PCP-ERP integration

Benefit Identified	Source	Main Impact
Greater operational efficiency through reduced bottlenecks and rework.	Tubino (2017); Correa; Corrêa (2017); Kasper et al. (2024).	Optimization of production processes and better use of resources.

Real-time visibility of operations	Laudon and Laudon (2015)	More assertive decision-making.
Cost and inventory reduction	Oliveira (2018)	Better financial and resource management.
Improved customer service	Slack; Brandon-Jones; Johnston (2020).	Greater reliability in delivery times.
Strategic alignment between functional areas	Davenport (1998)	Integration of the operational and strategic levels.
Data-driven decision making guided by intelligence.	Kasper et al. (2024)	Greater accuracy and speed in production.
Reducing operational errors and rework.	Griend; Kusters; Trienekens (2024)	Improved reliability of the production flow.

Source: Prepared by the authors (2025).

4.2 CHALLENGES OF PCP-ERP INTEGRATION

Despite the benefits, the literature and case studies indicate that implementing integrated production planning and control (PPC) within ERP systems faces significant barriers. Table 2 outlines the main obstacles and their impacts.

Table 2 – Challenges identified in the PCP-ERP integration

Challenge Identified	Source	Main Impact
High implementation and maintenance costs.	Oliveira (2018).	Financial barrier for small and medium-sized industries.
Technical complexity in system parameterization.	Davenport (1998).	The need for continuous customization.
Cultural resistance from employees.	Correa and Correa (2017)	Difficulty in organizational adaptation.
Need for specialized training.	Slack; Brandon-Jones; Johnston (2020).	Additional investment in training.
Technological dependence and the risk of failures.	Laudon and Laudon (2015)	Vulnerability of production operation.
Risks of code defects and subsequent repairs.	Griend; Kusters; Trienekens (2024).	Interruptions in the production flow.
Technical barriers to integration with real-time data.	Mäule and Götte (2025).	Difficulty in maintaining reliable and up-to-date data.

Source: Prepared by the authors (2025).

The challenges identified are not limited to the technological sphere, but also include human, financial, and organizational factors. Case studies indicate that implementation failures generally stem from inadequate team preparation, resistance to change, and a lack of strategic planning, rather than from technological limitations per se (Slack; Brandon-Jones; Johnston, 2020; Griend; Kusters; Trienekens, 2024).

4.3 EVALUATION OF PCP-ERP INTEGRATION

The analysis of the benefits and challenges suggests that integrating PCP (Product Control Planning) and ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) should not be viewed merely as a technological initiative, but as a comprehensive organizational strategy encompassing people, processes, and technology.

In accordance with Kasper et al. (2024), modern production planning and control (PPC) structures, supported by Industry 4.0 technologies, permit the integration of human judgment with automated intelligence for real-time decision-making and the optimization of both production planning and control. This model reinforces the need for continuous integration with the ERP so that data generated on the factory floor can inform strategic and operational decisions.

Mäule and Götte (2025) highlight that, even in advanced systems, gaps persist in maintaining reliable data and in the complexity of system integration, reinforcing the importance of critical analysis and continuous monitoring.

Furthermore, Griend, Kusters and Trienekens (2024) indicate that even robust ERP systems can experience defects and interruptions that affect production, highlighting the need for preventive maintenance procedures and continuous staff training.

In summary, integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) with ERP offers clear benefits in efficiency, control, and flexibility. Still, successful implementation depends on strategic planning, cultural alignment, and investment in technology and people. These elements are fundamental to achieving gains that outweigh the obstacles and to enabling the organization to achieve sustainable competitiveness in the context of Industry 4.0.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The integration of Production Planning and Control (PPC) with ERP systems is a strategic element in modern industry, providing significant improvements in operational efficiency, operational visibility, cost reduction, and alignment across strategic, tactical, and operational levels. However, the challenges identified, which include technical barriers, organizational resistance, implementation and maintenance costs, show that simply adopting the technology is not enough; strategic planning, team training, and continuous system monitoring are necessary for the benefits to be fully realized.

The objective of this study was to analyze the benefits and challenges arising

from integrating Production Planning and Control (PPC) and Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), and the results presented indicate that this objective was achieved. The literature review, combined with case study analysis and recent research, allowed us to identify both the strategic gains and the practical obstacles to this integration, providing relevant support for managers and researchers in effectively implementing this synergy in the industry.

Among the limitations of this research, the study's exclusively bibliographic and descriptive nature stands out, which prevents generalizing the results to all industries or production contexts. Moreover, future research could incorporate empirical data from companies, expanding the practical validity of the conclusions and allowing quantitative analyses of the real impact of PCP-ERP integration on industrial performance.

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